

NOTES

and $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$. Colours of the complexes were dark grey and brown respectively. Several experiments were performed by using different volumes of each metal chloride solutions.

From the results it is concluded that reagent *p*-dimethyl amino anil of anthracene glyoxal is an effective gravimetric reagent for Pt(IV) and Pd(II). In the gravimetric experiments error was found of the order 0.2 to 1.0 and 0.5 to 1.5% respectively. Both the complexes were insoluble in aqueous acetic acid, ether, benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water. This method may be regarded of limited applicability as has been tried only in the acetic medium. Reagent is quite effective and specific in the presence of NiCl_2 , CuCl_2 , CuBr , FeCl_3 , MnCl_2 , $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, AgNO_3 , SmCl_3 , LaCl_3 and YCl_3 .

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References

1. R. K. UPADHYAY, R. C. SAXENA and R. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 158.
2. P. SINGH, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut Univ., 1971.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Group Limited, London, 1969.

Effect of Different Nitrogenous Fertilizers and Lime on the Availability of Manganese in Acid Soils

S. K. BANERJEE & N. C. DEBNATH

Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kalyani, Nadia

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MANGANESE is recognised as one of the trace elements in plant nutrition. There had been different indices for available manganese in soil¹. Water soluble plus exchangeable manganese is considered as available for plants². Easily reducible manganese is also considered as active which may be slowly available to plants. Active manganese status in soils depends upon a number of factors such as *pH*, mineralisation of organic matter, oxidation reduction potential in soils etc.³ Nitrogen and sulphur additions were shown to beneficially affect its availability to arable crops⁴. It is sometimes feared that acid producing nitrogenous fertilizers, especially those producing acidity even by hydrolysis, may increase the available manganese in acid soils to an extent of damaging crops by manganese toxicity. In view of that the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of three nitrogenous fertilizers, *viz.* ammonium sulphate, urea and calcium nitrate,

which differ in their acid producing ability, on the available manganese status in acid soils. The effect of liming on manganese availability was also studied.

Experimental

Three different acid soils (two from North Bengal *i.e.*, Naxalbari and Raidak and one from Birbhum District, Sriniketan) of West Bengal were collected. The relevant physico-chemical properties of the soils are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS

Properties	Soils		
	Naxalbari	Raidak	Sriniketan
<i>pH</i> (Soil : Water = 1 : 2)	5.5	4.6	5.2
Organic carbon (%)	1.07	1.59	0.65
C.E.C. (me/100 g)	10.8	17.0	8.0
Clay (%)	39.6	25.1	32.6

The soil samples (10 g.) were incubated for 15 days at $30^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ with moisture at 50% moisture holding capacity with the treatments (1) control, (2) ammonium sulphate, (3) urea, and (4) calcium nitrate at the rate of 200 lbs/N/acre and (5) lime to raise the soil *pH* initially to 6.8 to 7.0. Calcium oxide was used as the liming material. All the chemicals used were analytical grade. Water soluble, exchangeable and reducible manganese were extracted and determined by the method as described by Jackson⁵. The analyses were made in duplicate and the mean values have been presented in the Table 2.

TABLE 2—*pH* OF THE SOILS AFTER 15 DAYS OF INCUBATION

Treatments	Soils		
	Naxalbari	Raidak	Sriniketan
Control	5.8	4.9	5.3
Ammonium sulphate	5.4	4.6	4.9
Urea	5.7	5.2	5.2
Calcium nitrate	5.6	4.8	5.2
Lime	6.5	5.6	6.1

Results and Discussion

The *pH* of the incubated soils has been shown in Table 2 and the results of the effect of different treatments on various forms of soil manganese have been presented in Table 3.

The addition of the nitrogenous fertilizers led to an increase in water soluble manganese and it was found that the application of calcium nitrate released greatest quantity of manganese followed by ammonium sulphate and urea. The same sequence was

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TREATMENTS ON VARIOUS FORMS OF MANGANESE IN SOILS (PPM MN)

Treatments	Soils		
	Naxalbari	Raidak	Sriniketan
	Water soluble		
Control	1.1	2.2	2.1
Ammonium sulphate	1.7	4.0	5.5
Urea	1.3	2.8	3.2
Calcium nitrate	4.0	6.4	9.3
Lime	0.6	2.1	1.4
	Exchangeable		
Control	0.2	1.3	77.4
Ammonium sulphate	0.9	1.9	97.0
Urea	0.4	1.4	85.0
Calcium nitrate	12.1	2.1	186.2
Lime	0.2	0.1	16.4
	Available		
Control	1.3	3.5	79.5
Ammonium sulphate	2.6	5.9	102.5
Urea	1.7	4.2	88.2
Calcium nitrate	16.1	8.5	195.5
Lime	0.8	2.2	17.8
	Easily reducible		
Control	41.0	64.3	208.1
Ammonium sulphate	50.3	74.5	241.3
Urea	46.4	66.8	222.1
Calcium nitrate	54.0	88.8	255.2
Lime	43.5	70.8	221.7

obtained in the case of exchangeable and available manganese. The application of lime led to a decrease in water soluble, exchangeable and available forms of manganese due to increase in pH of the soils. Manganese is found in soils in more than one valence state. The divalent manganese is easily soluble. The changes from bivalent state to higher valent states take place at higher pH. So the addition of lime favoured oxidation, due to which there was a decrease in bivalent form of manganese. The increase in water soluble and exchangeable manganese by the addition of nitrogenous fertilizers may be due to the lowering of soil pH and microbial activity. Ammonium sulphate reduced the pH of soil more than urea. So in all cases ammonium sulphate led to an increase of exchangeable manganese over urea. Though the change in pH of the soils by the addition of calcium nitrate was not as high as that with ammonium sulphate, calcium nitrate showed greater effect in releasing water soluble and exchangeable

manganese. The greater effect of calcium nitrate in this respect over ammonium sulphate and urea may be due to two reasons :

- (i) the replacing power of Ca^{++} is more than that of NH_4^+ , and
- (ii) the addition of calcium nitrate increases the activity of microorganisms more by supplying calcium and nitrogen. Thereby, the microorganisms decompose the organic matter of the soils more intensively creating a condition favourable for the reduction of higher oxides of manganese to Mn^{++} form.

The higher values of water soluble manganese than the exchangeable form in the cases of Naxalbari and Raidak soils may be explained by the fact that the organic matter contents of these two soils were very high. Manganese has been found to be one of the most easily exchangeable bases⁶, especially under acid conditions⁷. During incubation the decomposition of organic matter produced some organic acids, the H^+ ions of which released the exchangeable manganese to the water soluble form. But the picture was different in Sriniketan soil as its organic matter content was quite low.

The various treatments, with the exception of lime, increased the easily reducible manganese content of the soils in the same sequence as was observed in the cases of water soluble and exchangeable manganese. Addition of lime led to an increase in easily reducible manganese. This may be due to the activity of microorganisms. Addition of lime changes the condition of the soil to a state which favours to increase the activity of microorganisms and the manganese which remains at higher valent states changes to a state which is easily reducible by a readily oxidisable organic compound (hydroquinone in the present case).

From the above results it may be concluded that the most highly acid producing fertilizer, ammonium sulphate, increases the available manganese status of acid soils immediately after its application, but the magnitude of increase is much less than that with calcium nitrate.

References

1. E. G. MULDER and F. C. GERRETSEN, *Advan. Agron.*, 1952, 4, 22.
2. T. D. BISWAS, *Indian J. Agri. Sci.*, 1951, 21, 97.
3. G. W. LEEPER, *Soil Sci.*, 1947, 63, 79.
4. S. L. TISDALE and B. R. BERTRAMSON, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1949, 14, 131.
5. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice Hall International, Inc., Englewood Cliffs, 1958.
6. R. R. RUPRECHT and F. W. MORSE, *Mass. Agric. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1917, 176, 134.
7. S. MATTSON, *J. Agric. Res.*, 1926, 33, 553.